

Next generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials

MPL coating procedure (D 3.9)

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Abbreviations and indices

Abbreviation	Explanation
AEMWE	Anion exchange membrane water electrolysis
AWE	Alkaline water electrolysis
PEMWE	Proton-exchange-membrane water electrolysis
HER	Hydrogen evolution reaction
MEA	Membrane electrode assembly
OER	Oxygen evolution reaction
PTL	Porous transport layer
MPL	Micro transport layer
PSEBS	Polystyrene-block-poly(ethylene-ran-butylene)-block-polystyrene
CCS	Catalyst coated substrate
CCM	Catalyst coated membrane

1 Summary

The porous transport layer (PTL) is one of the key components in a variety of gas evolving electrochemical conversion technologies from fuel cells to carbon dioxide reduction and electrolyzers. The PTL has several purposes in electrolyzers, including thermal and electrical conduction, mechanical support, pathways for delivery of reactant liquid water to the catalyst layer, and removal of gaseous phase from the reaction sites to the outlet. The importance of the PTL is shown in a number of previous studies for electrolyzers. Multifunctional PTL was developed by introducing Nickel-based micro porous layers (MPLs) on the top of stainless-steel PTL substrates using vacuum plasma spraying technique and tested as a gas diffusion layer in AEMWE. The Ni-based MPL coated PTLs were characterized by SEM, EDX and XRD and with electrolyser cell testing. This deliverable is to report about the development of improved PTL for NEWELY AEMWE cells for operation in pure water and dilute KOH solution and it reports about the finally selected PTLs for the NEWELY stack.

Optimized Plasma-coating of porous Nickel as microporous layer on multilayer stainless steel PTLs were demonstrated to improve performance in both cells operated in pure water as well as 0.1 M KOH solution for Catalyst-Coated-Membrane (CCM) electrodes.

As the project moved to Catalyst-Coated-Substrate (CCS) electrodes an option how to realize MPL coating on market-available stainless-steel PTLs of the thickness as required for the NEWELY cell was realized, however, the performance in the cell could not be evaluated due to time limitations.

Finally, the NEWELY stack is equipped with CCS electrodes supported on commercial stainless steel felts and carbon papers and the PTLs are commercial stainless steel multilayer filter-grids and porous graphite.

2 Introduction

Hydrogen (H_2) gas produced from water electrolysis from renewable electricity provides a path to largely replace fossil fuels. There are three low-temperature water-electrolysis technologies for H_2 production: traditional alkaline water electrolysis (AWE), proton-exchange-membrane water electrolysis (PEMWE), and anion-exchange-membrane water electrolysis (AEMWE). [1-8] AWE is the most mature technology among water electrolyzer technologies, while PEMWE is more efficient than AWE for the same hydrogen-production capacity. [9-11] These advantages of PEMWE originate from higher reaction rates of catalysts in acidic media as well as the presence of thin polymeric membrane allowing a more compact stack design compared with the AWE with thick and porous separator in the highly concentrated alkaline electrolyte. [9] Despite the advantage for PEMWE, its main challenge is high capital cost of key materials such as precious metal-based catalysts and cell components mostly made of or coated with Noble metals. [12-14] Moreover, high cost membranes with the fluorinated moieties used in PEMWE suffer from restricted range of chemical diversity, which limits their further improvement. These expensive metals are the only materials that can bear the highly corrosive acidic environment in PEMWE originating from the acidic nature of perfluorinated polymeric membrane under highly anodic potential. Therefore, presently, AWE is still the most employed technology for large-scale hydrogen production since it uses inexpensive non-precious based catalysts and much less expensive components. [15] In order to merge the advantages of both systems, a substantial progress has been made over the last decade to the development of anion AEMWE, in which new membrane with internal high pH called anion exchange membrane (AEM) is used, which can conduct anions instead of cations. [16-21] In principle, AEMWE, with the locally alkaline environment, allows for the use of inexpensive, non-precious-based catalyst materials and cell components, and the use of an ion-conductive membrane inhibits crossover of gaseous phases and supports higher current densities compared with traditional AWE [19,20]. For hydrogen to play a viable role towards ambitious decarbonization, it requires inexpensive clean hydrogen. From the technology perspective, the levelized cost of hydrogen by electrolysis can be reduced if the electrolyzers can operate without critical raw material and with low electricity consumption, using pure water or low concentrated KOH. AEMWE has potential of doing that by combining development of various components hand-in-hand such porous transport layers (PTL), catalysts and AEMs. However, it has been technologically challenging to have AEMWE that can operate at acceptable low voltages and high operating current densities in neutral pH or low KOH

concentration. This is the necessary breakthrough needed to be considered for industrial applications of this technology. The early developments have rightfully been focused either on improving the AEMs and ionomers or on developing highly active catalysts. Though promising performance was attained with precious metal-catalysts, it was significantly lower when non-precious-metals are used as catalysts on both cathode and anode sides. This suggests that more research is needed for further performance improvements in AEMWE using non-precious based catalysts.

While researchers continue to focus on performance gain in AEMWE through developments in ionic conductive membrane and high performance non-precious-metal based catalysts to address critical issues regarding the various voltage losses, PTLs and a deposited microporous layer (MPL) are an alternative perspective to address this. By understating the value of membrane and catalyst, other cell components can influence interfacial contact resistance and consequently affecting the overall cell performance.

Therefore, we look at a solution from a different perspective to solve this missing piece of the puzzle with a conductive MPLs as multifunctional liquid/gas diffusion layers. Nickel-based MPLs coated on stainless steel PTL were fabricated by vacuum plasma spraying for AEMWE, which are expected to improve the cell performance operating with pure water and low concentrated KOH. Nickel-based MPLs were produced by spraying commercial Ni-based powders by plasma spraying on the top of PTLs made of stainless steel.

DLR has developed MPL by thermal spraying on Ti PTLs, improving largely the performance of the electrolyzer at high current densities of PEMWE [22]. Moreover, an entire pore-graded PTL with optimized tortuosity and capillary pressure was also developed by plasma spraying [14]. Tests in PEMWE demonstrated high performance and a significant decrease in mass transport limitations. By experimental work supported by simulation the very high current density operation of PEMWE could be realized with the help of the MPL/PTL concept [23]. The advantages are:

- Protection of the stainless steel mesh type PTL against corrosion
- Decrease cell overpotential at high current densities
- Reduction in contact Ohmic Resistance
- Mitigation of the mass transport limitations

- Improvement of the anode catalyst utilization

The MPL allows the most performing water distribution and gas detachment efficiency under high current density operation.

1 Experimental

The schematic illustration of the multifunctional Ni-PTL fabrication using plasma spray method is depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. (a)Schematic illustration of plasma spray coating of MPL on PTL and (b) schematic structure of a thermal sprayed coating,¹⁵ (c) scheme of the AEMWE cell configurations with plasma spray coated PTLs

As can be seen in Fig. 1a, Ni-based alloy was coated on the top of PTL. Briefly, in plasma spraying (Fig. 1a), the powder was injected through injection nozzles into the plasma jet, where particles were accelerated and heated due to momentum and heat transfer between plasma and particles, and the quasi or fully molten (Fig. 1b) particles impacted on the substrate surface followed by flattening, solidification and consolidation to form electrode coating.¹⁵ Multiple layers are coated to form Ni-based MPLs. A high-velocity gas flow removes the molten powder alloy and atomizes it into large droplet, which is propelled toward the PTL as a substrate. On hitting the substrate,

each molten droplet splats of powder onto the surface forms a pancake-like structure that swiftly solidifies and covers the PTL surface. However, the mechanical properties of the plasma spray-based deposits are highly dependent on in-flight treatment of particles and inter particle cohesion, which requires the highly optimized parameters during the thermal spraying.

More details on the coating are given in NEWELY Report D3.2. Details and further information is also given in DLR publication by F. Razmjooei [24] reporting about similar activities as in the NEWELY project.

2 Physical characterisation

As can be seen in Fig. 2, three different substrates, two single meshes with different pore shapes (single mesh A), (single mesh B) and multiple mesh substrates were selected to be coated and tested in AEMWE cell.

Figure 2. Metallography image of PTLs with different substrates before and after coating (a,b) single mesh A, (d,e) single mesh B and (g,h) multiple mesh substrate. SEM image of (c) MPL coated single mesh A, (f) MPL coated single mesh B and (i) MPL coated multiple mesh.

The phase and crystal structure of the coated layers produced by plasma have been characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. Fig. 3 shows the XRD pattern of plasma Ni-based coated on the single mesh A giving the structural information of coated single mesh material. XRD analyses disclosed the presence of two metal oxide phases, iron oxides Fe_3O_4 (PDF No. 01-075-0449) appeared at 35.0176° , 41.3442° , 50.5405° , 74.4551° , and 89.2914° and nickel oxide NiO (PDF No. 04-006-6925) appeared at 43.3702° and 50.9159° . Some metallic nickel iron, $\text{Fe}_{0.8782}\text{Ni}_{0.1218}$ (PDF No. 04-008-8475) appeared at 51.9766° , 59.5103° , 89.5477° and 90.60° and metallic Ni (PDF No. 04-010-6148) appeared at 51.9766° , 60.8181° , and 91.6010° were also identified (Fig. 3). Carbon peak is also detected (PDF No. 04-013-0293) at 30.7273° .

Figure 3. XRD patterns of coated single mesh A.

The XRD pattern of plasma Ni-based coated on single mesh B shows the XRD pattern same as that of coated single mesh A, (Fig. 4). The major constituents formed during plasma spraying on single meshes, are Ni (PDF No. 04-010-6148), nickel iron (PDF No. 04-008-8475), in which iron could come from the substrate, carbon (PDF No. 04-013-0293), however, the analysis of coated single meshes also shows formation of oxides (Fe_3O_4 and NiO), which might reduce the overall conductivity of PTL.

Figure 4. XRD patterns of coated single mesh B.

The structural information of Ni-based coated multiple meshes is also analysed using XRD. The XRD analysis of coated multiple mesh also shows the presence of some metallic Nickel iron, $\text{Fe}_{0.8782}\text{Ni}_{0.1218}$ (PDF No. 04-008-8475) appeared at 51.9766, 59.5103, 89.5477 and 90.60 and metallic Ni (PDF No. 04-010-6148) appeared at 51.9766, 60.8181, and 91.6010 and carbon (PDF No. 04-013-0293) appeared at 30.7273 same as the coated single meshes, Fig. 5. However, the analysis of coated mesh almost shows no oxide formation but the formation of Ni carbide, Ni_3C (PDF No. 04-019-2869) with the main peak at 52.3°. To understand the reason of it more analysis is needed to be done on the substrates.

Figure 5. XRD patterns of coated multiple mesh.

Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS) technique is capable of producing elemental distribution maps, an example of which is shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 6 exhibits the SEM/elemental mapping of all plasma Ni-coated on different substrates (a) single mesh A, (b) single mesh B and (c) multiple mesh. In order to get the cross-sectional SEM/elemental mapping images, samples are embedded in to the resin (The applied resin is the mixture of resin and hardener with a mass ratio of 25:3). SEM images in Figure 6a, 6b and 6c show that the Ni-based MPL is homogeneously coated on all three different substrates. EDX mapping over the coated substrates showed that Ni-based MPL successfully coated on all three different substrates. All substrates showed enrichment in chromium and Fe, however; multiple mesh substrate also contains some Cu constituents. The peaks regarding the substrates were not detectable by XRD since the substrates were homogeneously coated by the Ni-based coating. The formation of metallic nickel iron, $\text{Fe}_{0.8782}\text{Ni}_{0.1218}$, which was detected in all the XRD patterns could be due to the reaction of Ni from the powder precursors with Fe originating from the substrates. No further enrichment of any other alloying elements was observed. The thickness of Ni@C layer was less than 100 μm , meeting the fundamental requirements of multifunctional PTLs.

Figure 6. SEM/elemental mapping of MPL coated (a) single mesh A, (b) single mesh B and (c) multiple mesh.

3 Electrochemical characterization

Electrochemical characterization was performed to investigate the influence of the different substrates on the AEMWE performance. Therefore, Ni-based MPL-coated on different substrates have been tested in AEMWE cell in pure water at 45 °C with the MEA based on Fumatech membrane and precious metals (Fumatech membrane, 3.25 mg/cm² Ir black, 1.06 mg/cm² 47 wt.% Pt/C and 10 wt.% FFA-3 ionomer). The MEA after pre-activation in diluted alkaline solution rinsed with distilled water and sandwiched between coated PTLs. PTLs were cleaned with diluted acid to remove the surface oxide, which usually forms on Ni-based substrate due to passivation. The performance of the single-cell based on the cell configuration with the above mentioned MEAs and different coated substrates in terms of polarization curves are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that for Ni-based coated multiple mesh, overall cell performance is better over the whole range of applied current densities than the coated single meshes. For example, the cell based on the multiple mesh achieves a cell potential of 1.75 V at 0.03 Acm⁻², which is lower than that of cells with single mesh A (3 V) and single mesh B (2.29 V) at the same current density. This positive behaviour could be due to the higher contact surface of MPL coated multiple mesh with the MEA. As can be seen in Fig. 7 the AEMWE cell with coated multiple mesh gave the possibility to run the cell under the higher current densities compared with the two other coated single meshes. Therefore, the different multilayer meshes could be used for MPL coating.

Figure 7. Comparison of polarization curves of three different coated substrates in pure water at 45 °C .

To see the effect of MPL coating with the MEA based on the project material, the coated PTLs (with multiple layers) were implemented in the AEMWE cell with MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project (anion exchange membrane

developed in the project and 2.1 mg/cm^2 CENmat anode catalyst, 3.3 mg/cm^2 CENmat cathode catalyst and PSEBS-DABCO (93:7 wt%) ionomer). The test was done in pure water at 60°C , Fig. 8. The cell with MEA based on the AEM and non-precious metal developed in the current project was able to reach to the reasonable high current density of 0.5 A cm^{-2} without any cell failure. However, the voltage obtained at current density of 0.5 A cm^{-2} is still not low enough to meet the general defined requirement for AEMWE. Therefore, the test was continued in very diluted alkaline condition (0.1M) to further see the effect of coated PTL.

Figure 8. The cell performance of cell with coated PTL (multiple mesh) with the MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project (anion exchange membrane developed in the project and 2.1 mg/cm^2 CENmat anode catalyst, 3.3 mg/cm^2 CENmat cathode catalyst and PSEBS-DABCO (93:7 wt%) ionomer) in pure water at 60°C . Comparison of uncoated PTL and MPL-coated PTL

To see the effect of MPL coating on the substrate, bare PTL (multiple mesh) and coated one were implemented in the AEMWE cell and tested in 0.1M KOH at 60°C . Fig. 9 shows the electrochemical cell performance of MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project (anion exchange membrane developed in the project and 2.1 mg/cm^2 CENmat anode catalyst, 3.3 mg/cm^2 CENmat cathode catalyst and PSEBS-DABCO (93:7 wt%) ionomer) with coated and uncoated PTLs (multiple mesh). The test was done in very diluted alkaline condition in 0.1M KOH at 60°C , Fig. 9 Ni-based coated multiple meshes improved the cell performance showing the lower voltage at whole range of current density compared with that of uncoated PTL. This could be due to lower contact resistance of Ni-based coated PTL compared with that of bare PTL. The cell with coated PTL shows the improvement of $>300 \text{ mV}$ at 0.5 A cm^{-2} , which is better than the value, which was targeted in the project to reach almost the same cell voltage improvement of 300 mV at much higher current density of 1 A cm^{-2} . This shows that the MPL coating successfully reduced the cell potential all over the range of current densities.

Figure 9. The performance of cell with coated PTL and bare PTL (multiple mesh) with the MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project (anion exchange membrane developed in the project and 2.1 mg/cm^2 CENmat anode catalyst, 3.3 mg/cm^2 CENmat cathode catalyst and PSEBS-DABCO (93:7 wt%) ionomer) in 0.1M KOH at 60°C .

The AEMWE cell with the MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project (anion exchange membrane developed in the project and 2.1 mg/cm^2 CENmat anode catalyst, 3.3 mg/cm^2 CENmat cathode catalyst and PSEBS-DABCO (93:7 wt%) ionomer) with coated and uncoated PTLs (multiple mesh) is also operated at higher current densities approximately up to 2 A cm^{-2} , and the attributed current-voltage polarization curves are shown in Fig. 10. The cell with coated PTL is still more efficient than the cell with bare PTL at high current densities. These results show that the coated-PTL increases the cell performance and does not lose any advantage even at higher current densities.

Figure 10. The cell performance of cell with coated PTL and bare PTL (multiple mesh) with the MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project (anion exchange membrane developed in the project and 2.1 mg/cm^2 CENmat anode catalyst, 3.3

mg/cm² CENmat cathode catalyst and PSEBS-DABCO (93:7 wt%) ionomer) in 0.1M KOH at 60 °C at higher current densities.

Conclusion MPL/PTL for CCM electrodes:

Here, different PTLs were developed by introducing Ni based-MPLs by using the vacuum plasma spray technique on the top of different PTLs, two different single mesh PTLs and multiple mesh PTL. All the different PTLs are applied into the AEMWE with precious-based metal MEA with the commercial membrane. The cell with the coated multiple mesh gave the possibility to run the cell under the higher current densities compared with the two other coated single meshes. The coated multiple mesh was also tested with MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal catalysts developed in this project. With this combination, the cell was able to reach to the reasonable high current density of 0.5 A cm⁻² without any cell failure. However, to reach to the higher current density at lower voltage, which can avoid and limit the cell component degradation the experiments were continued in slightly diluted KOH (0.1M) solution. To see the effect of MPL coating on the substrate, bare PTL (multiple mesh) and coated one were implemented in the AEMWE cell and tested in 0.1M KOH at 60 °C. At 0.5 A cm⁻² already the voltage reduction due to the MPL is > 300 mV, which is better than the value, which was targeted to reach, almost the same cell voltage improvement of 300 mV at much higher current densities of 1 A cm⁻². The AEMWE cell with the MEA based on the anion exchange membrane and non-precious metal developed in the project with coated and uncoated PTL is also operated at higher current densities up to 2 A cm⁻² in the same condition. The cell with coated PTL is still more efficient than the cell with bare PTL at high current densities. These results show that the coated-PTL increases the cell performance and does not lose any advantage even at higher current densities.

Overall cell performance of the MEAs at that stage of the project was still low, however the positive effect of the MPL/PTL coating could be demonstrated. Further project development showed that moving from CCM (catalyst coated membrane) to CCS (catalyst coated substrate) approach in 0.1M KOH could achieve the target performances, see NEWELY report D3.10 (25).

4 MPL/PTL for ProPuls cell for CCS electrodes

For preparing electrodes via the CCS (catalyst coated substrate) approach a smooth substrate surface with small pores is needed. This is due to the fact that the thin catalyst layer has a low lateral electrical conductivity and therefore the distance between contact points must be low. Furthermore, the mechanical stability of AEM is not very high, i.e, the local contact pressure must be low. Following the project idea the CCS electrode substrate should be a combined PTL with MPL, the PTL being stainless steel material, the MPL for durability reasons coated with Nickel. At the same time the substrate needed to have the right thickness to fit into the PTL space which is given in the Propuls cell and could not be changed for the single cell testing. To fulfil these requirements DLR selected stainless steel felts of 2 mm thickness that are quite compressible. They were coated with a Nickel MPL by Vacuum Plasma Spraying in the way described before. An alternative set of PTL/MPL was coated with Raney-Nickel i.e. NiAl-alloy, then leaching the aluminium to get a high nickel surface. Figure 11 shows a side view of the coated stainless steel felt. Then the MPL/PTL were sent to DLR (Oldenburg), compressed to their thickness as needed in the cell (1.3-1.4 mm) and electrodes were coated as reported in NEWELY Deliverable D3.8 and 3.10 [25].

Figure 11. Top left: uncoated side of SS felt. Top right: PTL coated with Raney Nickel onto the felt. Bottom: Side view of stainless steel felt PTL with Nickel MPL coating on top side

These electrodes were sent to FBK for single cell tests in the Propuls cell. The single cell tests were conducted in comparison to tests of CCS electrodes coated on thin stainless steel felt with sintered titanium PTL.

However, there was a systematic error in all these tests, probably a reverse of the anode and cathode connection, leading to very poor performance in all these tests. It can only be concluded from these tests that all alternatives of PTL and electrodes behaved approximately in the same way. However, the purpose of optimizing the PTL and MPL is primarily relevant at high current densities. As these could not be reached in the tests it cannot be concluded if the MPL-coated stainless steel felt PTL give an improvement to other MPL and electrode substrates used in the project.

As the testing and plasma spraying capacities in the project did not allow further tries with MPL/PTL, this research path was abandoned and is to be verified in later projects.

MPL and electrode substrates for the stack:

For the final single cell testing as well as the stack assembly the following commercial electrode substrates and PTL are selected:

Anode electrode support: SS Bekipor 40BL3² (Bekaert) stainless steel felt, 230 μm thickness

Anode PTL: SS PTL by Haver³ for anode, stainless steel multilayer mesh for filtering applications

Cathode electrode support: Avcarb⁴ MGL370 Carbon paper, 370 μm thickness

Cathode PTL: LinqCell graphite for cathode⁵, porous graphite thickness 1.5 mm

The excellent performance of this material as electrode support and PTL in combination with NEWELY catalysts, membrane, ionomer, electrode preparation method and cell setup is demonstrated and reported in in NEWELY Deliverable D3.8 and 3.10 [25] achieving a performance of 2V at 1.48 A/cm² in 0.1M KOH at 50°C.

² Felt, material stainless steel 316L, 230 μm thickness, 12 μm fibres, 84 % Porosity

³ Haver&Boecker Haver POROSTAR, 5-La 5 μm , material Stainless steel 1.4404, filter material, sintered woven SS fibre grids, 5 layers of various pore thickness, minimum pore size 5 μm , thickness approx. 1.7 mm

⁴ <https://www.avcarb.com/product-page-mgl/> AvCarb® Molded Graphite Laminates (MGL) are superior carbon papers designed for electrolyzer and fuel cell applications. Porosity 78 %, thickness 0.370 mm

⁵ Thickness 1.5 mm, density 0.6 kg/m³, <https://www.caplinq.com/gdl1500-1.5mm-graphitized-carbon-plate-for-gas-diffusion-layers-gdl1500.html?filter=76523>

5 Conclusion

The PTL has several purposes in electrolyzers, including thermal and electrical conduction, mechanical support, pathways for delivery of reactant liquid water to the catalyst layer, and removal of gaseous phase from the reaction sites to the outlet. By introducing Nickel-based micro porous layers (MPLs) on the top of stainless-steel PTL substrates using vacuum plasma spraying technique an optimisation of PTL properties was achieved that demonstrated an overpotential reduction of more than 300 mV at 1 A/cm² in 0.1M KOH as compared to uncoated PTL using CCM electrodes. In pure water the overpotential reduction due to the optimized MPL/PTL was even higher demonstrating that this is an important component to further bring AEMWE technology with non-corrosive water feed to a promising performance comparable to other technologies.

For Catalyst-Coated-Substrate (CCS) electrodes PTL with plasma-coated MPL were realized and used as substrates for electrodes. Unfortunately, the test of these failed due to test station reasons and could not be repeated. This very promising option allowing many ways of optimisation remains to be demonstrated and further developed in future projects.

Finally, the NEWELY stack is equipped with CCS electrodes supported on commercial stainless steel felts and carbon papers and the PTLs are commercial stainless steel multilayer filter-grids and porous graphite.

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